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PARALLEL DISCIPLINES: EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN GLOBAL AND ETHICS LEARNING OF UNDERGRADUATE ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

As globalization of technological systems proceeds and design problems become increasingly complex, preparing future engineers for this rapidly changing world is a top priority. Both accreditation boards and disciplinary organizations alike have recognized the importance of global and ethics educations as a core component of the engineering curriculum. While often thought of as largely different disciplines of knowledge, universities across the country are placing more of an emphasis on these two disciplines, some going as far as to incorporate them across the entire general education curriculum. This study seeks to shed light on the connections that global and ethics education may have. To study this correlation, this pilot study utilized the Global Perspective Inventory, a validated, web-based assessment that measures global learning across the cognitive, interpersonal, and intrapersonal dimensions. To parallel the Global Perspective Inventory, we constructed various survey items that paralleled the survey items, but with a focus on ethical identity and awareness. We distributed the modified survey to undergraduate engineering students at Virginia Tech. Through the use of paired t-tests, preliminary analysis of a small pilot group indicates a strong correlation across 8 of the 19 survey item pairs. More findings will be shared in the final draft. As we continue to further our understanding of both global and ethics educations in the engineering curriculum, we hope to increase the sample size of our study and incorporate various demographic factors to improve our understanding of global and ethics education.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Both ethical and global competencies have been highlighted as vital components of the engineering education curriculum. In the most recent accreditation criteria, ABET (the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology) stresses the importance of recognizing ethical responsibilities and considering their impact in both a global and societal context [1]. Similarly, the National Academy of Engineering (NAE) has outlined a need for engineering graduates to be prepared to address ethical considerations of engineering problems while working in multicultural and global teams [2]. As national and disciplinary organizations place more of an emphasis on ethical and global competencies for graduating engineering students, many engineering universities, departments, and faculty are doing the same.

While ethics and global education are often conceptualized differently, many similarities exist between the two competencies. Pedagogies used in engineering course work, such as case studies and role play, offers a platform for combining ethics and global education. Dempsey, Stamets, and Eggleston (2016) designed a role play scenario in which students practiced the skills of perspective-taking and empathy, each of which are components of moral development but also benefit a global engineer [3]. Sustainability is another area in which global and ethics education overlap. In examining the trends of sustainability in engineering education, Tejedor et al. (2018) found that words such as transdisciplinary, ethics, and networking all were increasing in sustainability education [4]. Shedding light on the relationship between ethical and global competencies is needed to identify how these two competencies can be included in a curriculum that will develop more holistic engineers.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Ethics Education

Ethics education has often been broken down into two general fields of study, microethics and macroethics. Microethics is concerned with issues at the individual level, such as responsible conduct of research (RCR) and conflicts of interest. Macroethics looks at the bigger picture, which can include discussions of sustainability and privacy [5], [6]. While microethics are more commonly taught in undergraduate engineering courses and may help students avoid certain pitfalls, macroethics helps students look at ethical dilemmas from a bigger picture, providing them with a more comprehensive view of the situation [7].

Ethics education is most commonly delivered in the classroom through case studies, which are either short stories of fictional or historical events, often revolving around the decision-making of an organization or individual. Students then respond to questions, individually, in groups, or as a class, to discuss the nuances of the ethical dilemma the agents in the stories faced [7]–[9]. An objective of this pedagogy is to have students think through realistic problems and come to a plan of action through collaborative perspective taking. Roleplaying and games are among the other pedagogies commonly employed by ethics education faculty across disciplines. Games similar to those described in Sadowski et al. are designed to engage students with ethical quandaries through the lens of reason rather than rules [10]. Role play, similar to case studies, allows students to examine a moral dilemma from

another's perspective [11]. However, by roleplaying as another individual, students may take on a self-oriented approach as opposed to an other-oriented approach [12]. By taking on a self-oriented approach, students can imagine how they would act or feel if they were the person in the story, as opposed to simply imagining how that person might feel [13].

2.2 Global Education

In the context of this paper, global education refers to education specifically designed to prepare students to navigate a globalized and culturally diverse world more effectively. Prompted by this idea of a global marketplace, one component of engineering education that has become prominent is designing for international communities and working in interdisciplinary and multinational teams [14], [15]. The impetus for global education in the design context is that it promotes both creativity and open-mindedness [16]. Students must be prepared to work in international settings with international goals in the foreseeable future [17].

Study abroad programs offer unique opportunities for some engineering students to develop global competencies. By visiting another country or culture for anywhere from a week to a summer, students have the opportunity to learn about and be immersed in a different culture. By providing avenues for students to experience other cultures, students might expand their worldview, and in doing so learn the value of working with individuals from different backgrounds from themselves. Similarly, opportunities such as Engineering without Borders and the Semester at Sea also provide globally-oriented experiences to engineering students [18]. Another approach that allows students to engage with global competencies is through projects with international and multicultural partners, such as where these might replace or act as extensions to current capstone and design projects [17]. However, some authors have noted that such programs, whether inter- or intra-cultural, require significant contextual preparation to avoid counterproductive outcomes, with disparities in social capital among participants being an especially conspicuous obstacle [19]. Part of this preparation involves development of cognitive and social skills, which may be applicable in both intercultural and ethical domains. Examining the overlap between these domains in the context of undergraduate engineering education is our primary focus here.

2.3 Parallels and the Global Perspective Inventory

The Global Perspective Inventory (GPI) is a validated survey instrument developed at Iowa State University that examines the cognitive, intrapersonal, and interpersonal dimensions of an individual's ability to take the perspectives of others into account. It is grounded in cultural development and intercultural communication theories.

Cultural development theory outlines three domains, the cognitive, the intrapersonal, and the interpersonal through which students construct meaning and make sense of the world around them [20].

Intercultural communication theory emphasizes three important domains for success in communicating in intercultural contexts: the affective, the cognitive, and the

behavioral [20]. These three domains also appear in empathy literature, which has been operationalized in engineering ethics literature as the ethics of care [21]. In fact, empathy seems to be at the core of what connects the theoretical underpinnings of global and ethics education. Segal (2011) defines empathy as “the ability to understand people by perceiving or experiencing their life situations and as a result gain insight into structural inequalities and disparities” [22]. In the domain of engineering ethics, empathy allows engineers to incorporate the perspectives of stakeholders and customers into the decision-making process. As a parallel to this, in the domain of global engineering, empathy allows engineers to incorporate the perspectives of those with different cultural and national backgrounds. The GPI is a validated tool for measuring the perspective taking ability of students with different global contexts. With this connection of empathy in mind, we have adapted the GPI to also measure the perspective taking ability of students in the context of ethics as well.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Aims

The goal of this research was to examine the parallels between ethics and global education through the use of the GPI survey. By creating questions that directly parallel the GPI with ethical counterparts, our aim is to understand how perspective taking in these two domains relate. We anticipate that our research will show how to conduct research and design pedagogies for improving the global and ethical competencies of our students. To accomplish these research aims, we sought to answer these specific questions:

RQ1. How do global and ethical perspective-taking relate to each other?

3.2 Settings and Participants

To answer this research question, we conducted a preliminary study at a large comprehensive, engineering focused, university in the US (Virginia Tech). At the time of data collection, the undergraduate engineering population was 6,000 students. Students were recruited from a plethora of senior capstone and first-year general education courses, across disciplines.

Students were informed of the study in one of their prior class sessions and provided the opportunity and time to complete the survey during class time, which took approximately 5 minutes. Faculty members were given the option to provide students with extra credit. Only those who provided consent (as granted during the first question of the survey), were included in the survey. This study was approved by the Virginia Tech’s Institutional Review Board. The self-selected sample consisted of approximately 220 students.

3.3 Global Perspective Inventory

The survey instrument consisted of two portions, the Global Perspective Inventory (GPI) and the Ethical Perspective Inventory (EPI) extension. Both the GPI and the EPI utilize Likert-like responses ranging from ‘Strongly Disagree’ to ‘Strongly Agree.’ The GPI is divided into three domains, the cognitive, intrapersonal, and

interpersonal, each of which contains two subscales. The cognitive dimension pertains to thinking and is divided into the knowing and knowledge subscales. Knowing refers to the complexity of thinking about multicultural issues while knowledge refers to the knowledge the student has of multicultural issues. The intrapersonal dimension is divided into identity and affect. The former pertains to an individual's understanding and accepting of their personal sense of purpose while the latter refers to how much in individual respects and accepts the differences between them and others. The third domain is the interpersonal domain, which refers to how one interacts with others, and is divided into two subscales, the social responsibility scale and the social interaction scale. The social responsibility scale pertains to an individual having concern for others and the social interaction scale relates to the affinity one has for engaging with others who are from different backgrounds. The number of survey items pertaining to each subscale can be seen below in Table 1. The full list of survey items can be found below in Appendix A.

3.4 Ethical Perspective Index Extension

To create the corollary survey items for examining ethical perspectives of students, our research team first outlined which survey items we thought needed to be altered. The standard GPI instrument consists of 35 questions. Of these, 16 can be straightforwardly construed as probing ethical perspectives in their original form. For example, the statement "In different settings what is right and wrong is simple to determine" has obvious ethical implications, and can reasonably be applied in both global/intercultural situations and local/intracultural ones. In this sense, almost half of the standard GPI should already be considered a direct survey of ethical perspectives. The remaining 19 survey items in the GPI are, instead, specific to intercultural contexts, and were altered to create the EPI extension. The purpose of this extension is to provide a parallel set of questions that eliminate any references to cultural differences and replace those with value differences instead. As an example, "I intentionally involve people from many cultural backgrounds in my life" from the GPI was altered to "I intentionally involve people with different viewpoints in my life". This shift in wording re-contextualizes the question to focus on differences in attitude instead of differences in identity. Comparison of responses to this pair of questions can thus serve to probe the correlation between ethical and intercultural perspectives. Once the survey items to be altered had been decided upon, the team created multiple alternative survey items for each corollary in the EPI and discussed each one at length, consulting experts outside of the research team to ensure that each survey item was appropriate and parallel to the GPI survey item. The breakdown of added questions can be seen across domains and subscales in Table 1. The full survey can be seen in Appendix A.

Table 1. Summary of Survey Items

Survey Section/Scale	Subscale	Items
Global Perspective Inventory (35 Items)	Cognitive Knowing (CogEp)	7
	Cognitive Knowledge (CogKnw)	5
	Identity (Ident)	6
	Affect (Affect)	5
	Social Responsibility (SocRes)	5
	Social Interactions (SocInt)	4
	Global Citizen (GloCit)	1
	Threat (Threat)	1
	Comfort (Comfor)	1
Ethical Perspective Inventory (19 Items)	Cognitive Knowing (EthCogEp)	5
	Cognitive Knowledge (EthCogKnw)	5
	Identity (EthIdent)	1
	Affect (EthAffect)	1
	Social Responsibility (EthSocRes)	1
	Social Interactions (EthSocInt)	4
	Global Citizen (EthGloCit)	1
	Threat	1
Total Items	54	

4 RESULTS

Prior to analysis, the data was cleaned, reverse-coded items were inverted, and the Likert-like responses were converted to a nominal scale. The responses were multiple choice and ranged from ‘Strongly Disagree’ to ‘Strongly Agree,’ which were changed to a 1 to 5 scale for the analysis portion of this paper. The analysis section of this research includes confirmatory factor analysis to determine the consistency of the questions within each scale, followed by paired t-tests to show that there are discernable differences between the GPI and the ethical questions we created in this research.

4.1 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed to ensure internal consistency across the scales of the GPI, as well as to determine if the questions that were altered to create the EPI were consistent with the GPI survey items. CFA is a tool used to ensure that all items on a given scale are correlated to one another. The constructs described in the GPI are valuable insofar that they examine how a student perceives their own moral values, as well as how their moral values influence how they interact with other. We utilize confirmatory factory analysis in an attempt to define constructs that can later be used to see how students develop these abilities over time.

In our examination of the scales depicted in Table 2, we examined three goodness of fit statistics, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation, (RMSEA), the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI). The RMSEA is an absolute fit index based on chi-squared, degrees of freedom and the sample size.

Because the RMSEA is absolute, issues can arise when interpreting results from small models. However, with the given sample size (N=221), we also examined CFI and TLI, which has been shown to provide reasonable fits for models similar to ours in size [23]. An RMSEA of 0 indicates a perfect fit, while a moderate fit is generally considered under 0.08. The CFI and TLI are considered to have good fits if there are above 0.95 as they approach 1. Table 2 depicts that four of the six scales in the GPI containing more than one item were found to have a good fit, while cognitive knowledge potentially had a moderate fit. The cognitive knowledge and identity scales were not found to have great internal consistency, across the three measure goodness of fit statistics.

Table 2. Confirmatory factor analysis for GPI subscales

Scale	Measure of Goodness of Fit	Value	Classification
Cognitive Knowing (CogEp)	RMSEA	0.096	Not a Good Fit
	CFI	0.799	Not a Good Fit
	TLI	0.699	Not a Good Fit
Cognitive Knowledge (CogKnw)	RMSEA	0.070	Moderate Fit
	CFI	0.978	Good Fit
	TLI	0.955	Good Fit
Identity (Ident)	RMSEA	0.137	Not a Good Fit
	CFI	0.839	Not a Good Fit
	TLI	0.732	Not a Good Fit
Affect (Affect)	RMSEA	0.000	Good Fit
	CFI	1.000	Good Fit
	TLI	1.003	Good Fit
Social Responsibility (SocRes)	RMSEA	0.015	Good Fit
	CFI	0.999	Good Fit
	TLI	0.997	Good Fit
Social Interactions (SocInt)	RMSEA	0.030	Good Fit
	CFI	0.997	Good Fit
	TLI	0.990	Good Fit

To examine the EPI scales, researchers first substituted the relevant questions to create the ethical subscales based on the GPI scales. This was done by replacing the questions indicated in column 1 of Table 4 with the question indicated in column 2 of the table. The full questions can be seen in Appendix A. Similar to the finding from Table 1, both the cognitive knowing and the identity scales did not show good a fit, while cognitive knowing, affect, social responsibility, and social interactions all displayed a good fit across all three goodness of fit statistics.

Table 3. Confirmatory factor analysis for EPI subscales

Scale	Measure of Goodness of Fit	Value	Classification
EthCogEp	RMSEA	0.124	Not a Good Fit
	CFI	0.658	Not a Good Fit
	TLI	0.488	Not a Good Fit
EthCogKnw	RMSEA	0.037	Good Fit
	CFI	0.992	Good Fit
	TLI	0.985	Good Fit
EthIdent	RMSEA	0.074	Not a Good Fit
	CFI	0.934	Not a Good Fit
	TLI	0.891	Not a Good Fit
EthAffect	RMSEA	0.000	Good Fit
	CFI	1.000	Good Fit
	TLI	1.055	Good Fit
EthSocRes	RMSEA	0.000	Good Fit
	CFI	1.000	Good Fit
	TLI	1.028	Good Fit
EthSocInt	RMSEA	0.000	Good Fit
	CFI	1.000	Good Fit
	TLI	1.013	Good Fit

4.2 Paired Sample T-Tests

After examining the internal consistency within each subscale, it was important to ensure concurrent validity, that the EPI and GPI corollaries were measuring distinctly different measures. To do this we ran 19 separate paired sample t-tests, one for each EPI/GPI corollary to determine if there was a statistical difference between the means of each survey item. The results of the analysis found that of the 19 item pairs, ten pairs were significantly different with a 99% confidence interval, while an additional two survey pairs were significantly different with a 95% confidence interval.

Table 4. Paired sample t-test results across GPI and ethics equivalent

GPI Question	EPI Question	T	df	Sig. (two-tailed)
CogEp01	EthCopEp01	3.9773	220	0.0001**
Ident02	EthIdent02	-0.90545	220	0.3662
SocInt04	EthSocInt04	1.8829	220	0.0610
SocRes05	EthSocRes05	5.0611	220	0**
CogEp06	EthCogEp06	18.811	220	0**
CogKnw08	EthCogKnw08	-6.4766	220	0**
Threat10	EthThreat10	4.6933	220	0**
CogKnw13	EthCogKnw13	-2.8592	220	0.0047**
GloCit15	EthGloCit15	2.4108	220	0.01674*
CogKnw17	EthCogKnw17	-1.9928	220	0.0475*
CogEp19	EthCogEp19	2.6853	220	0.0078**
CogEp20	EthCogEp20	-0.15042	220	0.8806
CogKnw21	EthCogKnw21	-1.6311	220	0.1043
SocInt24	EthSocInt24	1.158	220	0.2481
CogKnw27	EthCogKnw27	-1.537	220	0.1257
SocInt29	EthSocInt29	-0.36889	220	0.7126
CogEp30	EthCogEp30	3.4401	220	0.0007**
Affect31	EthAffect31	3.6768	220	0.0003**
SocInt35	EthSocInt35	-8.2049	220	0**

*indicates a 95% confidence interval

**indicates a 99% confidence interval

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study sought to examine how global and ethical perspective-taking parallel each other across a variety of dimensions. We first set out to show that the subscales of the GPI were internally consistent, to both create a baseline for consistency when we would start to alter items for the EPI, as well as bring the GPI to new settings to help determine the generalizability of the survey. While only 4 of the 6 subscales indicated good statistical fits, there is the possibility that this is due to a lower sample size (N~220), which we seek to expand upon in the future.

After determining the internal consistency of the GPI scales, our examination of the EPI scales, with the 19 items switched out for their corollaries, resulted in the same 4 subscales having good fit. In the case of the identity subscale, it is likely that because only 1 item was changed between subscales, and there was no statistical difference between the two from the t-test, the goodness of fits were results of nearly identical data. However, the same could not be said for the cognitive knowing

subscales. The first inclination was that there was the possibility that the survey items for each subscale were too similar, like the identity subscales, which could have led to the same goodness of fit results across the subscales. However, in the case of the cognitive knowing subscale, 5 of the 7 items were switched between scales, 4 of which had significant differences between the two subscales. Of the 7 items that did not produce significant differences with the paired t-tests, three of the items were part of the social interaction subscale. There are a few reasons that this could have happened for this particular subscale. First and foremost, it is possible that the changes to the survey items were not impactful enough to make statistical differences. More likely, however, is the fact that these surveys were distributed electronically during the COVID-19 pandemic, during which a majority of classes transitioned to remote learning, and social interactions decreased drastically, both in and out of the classroom. Because of this, it is difficult to make any further claims as to why the social interaction subscales did not differ. These results are the first step to identifying the relationship between global and ethical perspective-taking. We have provided evidence that when modifying items from the existing Global Perspective Inventory, we can create statistically different yet internally consistent subscales that measure aspects of both global and ethics education. Moving forward, we plan to continue to increase our sample size, so as to increase the internal consistency of the data and the external validity of the study. Additionally, we will continue to discuss and iteratively make changes to survey items to ensure statistical differences between the two. As we create distinctions between the two instruments, we will begin to examine how ethical and global constructs develop throughout the duration of higher education, and seek to expand our work to a plethora of other institutions, but within and outside of the United States.

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APPENDIX A. GPI/EPI SURVEY ITEMS

CogEp01	When I notice cultural differences, my culture tends to have the better approach. (R) <i>(R)-Reversed Item</i> <i>Note: This item was reverse coded from the original survey format (1 = Strongly disagree to 5 =strongly agree) to the correct format (1 = strongly agree to 5 = strong disagree).</i>
Ident02	I have a definite purpose in my life.
Ident03	I can explain my personal values to people who are different from me.
SocInt04	Most of my friends are from my own ethnic background. (R)
SocRes05	I think of my life in terms of giving back to society
CogEp06	Some people have a culture and others do not. (R)
CogEp07	In different settings what is right and wrong is simple to determine. (R)
CogKnw08	I am informed of current issues that impact international relations
Ident09	I know who I am as a person.
Threat10	I feel threatened around people from backgrounds different from my own. (R)
Comfor11	I often get out of my comfort zone to better understand myself.
Ident12	I am willing to defend my own views when they differ from others.
CogKnw13	I understand the reasons and causes of conflict among nations of different cultures.
SocRes14	I work for the rights of others.
GloCit15	I see myself as a global citizen.
CogEp16	I take into account different perspectives before drawing conclusions about the world around me.
CogKnw17	I understand how various cultures of this world interact socially.
Ident18	I put my beliefs into action by standing up for my principles.
CogEp19	I consider different cultural perspectives when evaluating global problems.

CogEp20	I rely primarily on authorities to determine what is true in the world. (R)
CogKnw21	I know how to analyze the basic characteristics of a culture.
Affect22	I am sensitive to those who are discriminated against.
Affect23	I do not feel threatened emotionally when presented with multiple perspectives.
SocInt24	I frequently interact with people from a race/ethnic group different from my own.
Affect25	I am accepting of people with different religious and spiritual traditions.
SocRes26	I put the needs of others above my own personal wants.
CogKnw27	I can discuss cultural differences from an informed perspective.
Ident28	I am developing a meaningful philosophy of life.
SocInt29	I intentionally involve people from many cultural backgrounds in my life.
CogEp30	I rarely question what I have been taught about the world around me. (R)
Affect31	I enjoy when my friends from other cultures teach me about our cultural differences.
SocRes32	I consciously behave in terms of making a difference.
Affect33	I am open to people who strive to live lives very differently from my own life style.
SocRes34	Volunteering is not an important priority in my life. (R)
SocInt35	I frequently interact with people from a country different from my own.
EthCogEp01	When I notice differences in values, I generally believe my values are better.
EthIdent02	I have a distinct set of ethical convictions.
EthSocInt04	Most of my friends share my point of view about day-to-day issues.
EthSocRes05	I think of my life in terms of justice.
EthCogEp06	Some people are ethical and others are not.
EthCogKnw08	I am informed of/about current moral issues in society.
EthThreat10	I feel threatened around people who display values different from my own.
EthCogKnw13	I understand the reasons and causes of conflict among people with different values.
EthGloCit15	I see myself as part of a like-minded community.
EthCogKnw17	I understand how diverse groups of people interact in society.

- EthCogEp19 I consider different ethical perspectives when evaluating interpersonal problems.
- EthCogEp20 I rely primarily on authorities to determine what is right or good for me to do.
- EthCogKnw21 I know how to analyze the basic characteristics of value systems.
- EthSocInt24 I frequently interact with people that hold values different from my own.
- EthCogKnw27 I can discuss value differences from an informed perspective.
- EthSocInt29 I intentionally involve people with different viewpoints in my life.
- EthCogEp30 I rarely question what I have been taught about right and wrong.
- EthAffect31 I enjoy when friends with other perspectives or beliefs teach me about our differences.
- EthSocInt35 I frequently interact with people who think differently from me.